

Location

Spain (Murcia – Cartagena, La Junquera)

Key Issues

- » **Low biodiversity, poor soil structure, and low organic matter.**
- » High levels of erosion and **excessive use of water and nutrients.**
- » High soil pH (>8) reduces nutrient availability → **constant fertilizers input.**
- » Semiarid climate with **low water availability and limited water-holding capacity.**
- » Resulting in **high production costs, soil degradation, and water pollution.**

SoildiverAgro Approach

Four strategies tested in irrigated systems:

- » Standard **mineral fertilization.**
- » **F50:** 50% reduced mineral fertilization.
- » **F50 + biostimulants** (PGPR bacteria).
- » **F50 + biostimulants + fungi** (non-mycorrhizal).
- » **Main objective:** Reduce fertilizer dependency while improving **soil biodiversity, crop yield, and long-term sustainability.**

Benefits

- » **Biostimulants** reduce **fertilizer use** and enhance **microbial balance.**
- » **Precision agriculture** lowers **input costs.**
- » **Fertilizer optimization** supports **organic** cereal **production.**
- » Implemented measures mitigate **soil degradation** and reduce **water pollution.**

Within the **Mediterranean South pedoclimatic region**, the case studies conducted as part of the SoildiverAgro Project focused on the Region of Murcia, Spain, an area characterized by intensive agricultural activity, mostly focused on irrigated vegetable, citrus, and fruit production, and, to a lesser extent, on rainfed cereal, olive, and almond production.

This region is currently facing significant agricultural challenges, including a **low below and aboveground biodiversity, a high erosion rate, low soil organic matter content, weak soil structure, low nutrient availability, and excessive use of water and nutrients**, resulting in systems with high production costs, soil degradation, and water pollution.

Another challenge lies in the fact that nutrient availability is very low in these soils due to pH values exceeding 8, necessitating the continuous addition of fertilizers. In addition, the climate is semiarid, with low water availability and limited soil water-holding capacity.

Given these major challenges, several sustainable agricultural strategies have been tested in this area, including:

1. Mineral fertilizers applied to the nutritional demands of the crop.
2. It was 50% of the rate of mineral fertilizers needed to ensure the nutritional demands of the crop (F50).
3. F50 + application of biostimulants (a formulation of nitrogen-fixing and phosphorus and potassium solubilizing bacteria); and
4. F50 + application of biostimulants (a formulation of nitrogen-fixing and phosphorus and potassium solubilizing bacteria and non-mycorrhizal fungi).

The main objectives of these practices were to reduce the use of external fertilizers while increasing soil biodiversity and maintaining—or even improving—agricultural yields. Improved soil biodiversity is also expected to enhance overall soil health and fertility in the medium to long term, contributing to the resilience and sustainability of agricultural systems.

Results

Based on the results obtained in this project, the following policy recommendations are proposed:

- Promote the addition of microbial inoculants in Mediterranean irrigated horticulture, particularly when plant growth-promoting bacteria and fungi are applied together, to reduce the dependency on mineral fertilizers.** This strategy can decrease the carbon footprint of the farm and stimulate beneficial microorganisms that help maintain high crop yields and reduce the abundance and incidence of soil pathogens.

- Encourage precision agriculture to decrease the use of fertilizers, since they can be reduced and optimized without affecting crop yield or quality.**
- In rainfed arable crops, encourage fertilizer optimization,** which could be reduced in cereal production under organic management without negatively affecting crop yield and quality.
- The use of microbial inoculants may not be effective for rainfed cereal production under a Mediterranean climate, as no increases in crop yield or quality were observed.

From the **SoildiverAgro** project perspective, the implementation of these policy recommendations would significantly enhance the competitiveness of the agricultural sector in this region, while also increasing the long-term resilience and sustainability of agricultural systems—primarily through improved biodiversity and enhanced soil ecosystem services.

Finally, it is important to emphasize that these measures would also contribute substantially to reducing soil degradation and water pollution.

